

Analytical Applications of 2-Hydroxy-3-Chloro-5-Methylacetophenone Oxime (Hcmao)—Part I : Reactions with Metal Ions and Gravimetric Determination of Copper

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2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methylacetophenone oxime has been found to be a wide-spectrum precipitant for a number of transition metal ions. It gives colour reactions with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{3+} . Cu^{2+} gives a buff coloured bis-chelate $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2\text{Cl})_2$ precipitated at a pH 2.5-6.0. About 15-65 mg of Cu^{2+} has been determined gravimetrically, the average error being less than one percent. Cu^{2+} in presence of moderate amounts (15-20 mg) of Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{3+} has been determined gravimetrically.

2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methylacetophenone oxime (HCMAO) has the system: $-\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{N}$ —similar to many precipitating agents used for a number of transition metal ions. Its effectiveness is particularly demonstrated in the precipitation of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. The reagents having such a system have been investigated by several workers¹⁻³. The investigations on the use of salicylaldoxime²⁻⁴, resacetophenone oxime^{5,6} and *o*-hydroxy-acetophenone oxime^{7,8} have led to the conclusion that the precipitation is a characteristic of the reagent and is influenced by the pH.

The present work on the reactions of HCMAO with Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions was undertaken with the intention to find the best conditions for gravimetric determinations using this reagent. The chelates obtained have been assigned constitutions similar to those of salicylaldoxime⁹ and *o*-hydroxy-ketoximes⁷.

The reaction of HCMAO with Cu^{2+} gives a buff coloured precipitate between the pH range 2.5 to 6.0. Cu^{2+} (15-65 mgm.) has been determined gravimetrically at a pH 2.5, the error being less than one per cent on the base of Cu^{2+} calculated. The ions like Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} are found not to interfere at a pH range 2.5 to 5.0. The interference of Fe^{3+} has been removed by masking it with potassium citrate. The precipitate can be safely dried between 110°-120°C within a period of 2 hr. The reagent has also been investigated for metal ions Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Fe^{3+} for colour reactions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of metal ions, prepared by dissolving pure salts in a double-distilled water, were used after

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standardisation by the standard methods. Solutions of cations (0.05M) were used in all the cases and the pH was adjusted using 6N acetic acid, 10% sodium acetate or 6N ammonium hydroxide solution depending upon the pH range desired.

Reagent: 2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methylacetophenone oxime: The ketone¹⁰ was obtained in almost quantitative yield by the Fries migration of 2-chloro-4-cresyl acetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

Its oxime was prepared by the reaction of the above ketone with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate in dilute ethanol. It was further purified by repeated crystallisations from ethanol, m.p. 215°C (decomp.) (Found: C, 53.2; H, 4.8; N, 6.8; Cl, 17.4; Calc. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$: C, 53.9; H, 5.1; N, 7.1; Cl, 17.8%).

Reactions of 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methylacetophenone oxime with some metal ions: A one per cent ethanolic solution of the reagent was used for the tests. It gave buff precipitate with Cu^{2+} at pH 2.5, violet colour with Fe^{3+} at pH 2.5-4.5, light green precipitate with Ni^{2+} at pH 5.0 and orange yellow precipitate with Co^{2+} at pH 6.5. Al^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and K^+ were found to give no insoluble chelates or colour formation.

Properties of the Copper complex: The copper bis-chelate $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{NCl})_2$ (Cu Calc.: 13.79 per cent. Found: 13.65%) with the reagent precipitated at a pH 2.5-3.0 (acetic acid+sodium acetate) is buff coloured and is insoluble in water, ethanol, ether and dilute acetic acid but soluble in chloroform. It can be dried at 110°-120°C.

Determination of Copper: A solution containing 31.4 mgs of Cu^{2+} was diluted to about 200 ml and the pH adjusted using an acetate buffer. The solution was warmed to 60°-70°C and a calculated

volume of an ethanolic solution of the reagent was added with stirring followed by about a 10 per cent excess to ensure a complete precipitation. The copper complex was digested at about 60°-70°C and allowed to stand for about 30 min and then filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G-4). The complex was washed with 50% ethanol, dried at 110°-120°C to a constant weight and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{NCl})_2$. It has been found that copper can be quantitatively determined in the pH range 2.5-6.0. Conversion factor for Cu^{2+} is 0.1379. The results of some of the estimations are given in Table 1.

 TABLE 1. GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF Cu^{2+} AT pH 2.5-3.0

Serial No.	Cu^{2+} taken in mg.	Cu^{2+} complex in mg.	Cu^{2+} found in mg.	Error in mg.
1.	15.8	118.0	16.2	+0.4
2.	23.5	170.0	23.3	-0.2
3.	31.4	228.0	31.2	-0.2
4.	47.0	345.0	47.2	+0.2
5.	62.9	458.0	62.7	-0.2

Estimation of Cu^{2+} in presence of other ions : The pH range in which the precipitation of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} begins is much above the pH for complete precipitation of Cu^{2+} . It was therefore possible to determine Cu^{2+} at a pH 2.5 in the presence of these ions. Table 2 gives the results of determination of

 TABLE 2. ESTIMATION OF Cu^{2+} AT pH 2.5 IN PRESENCE OF OTHER IONS

Cu ²⁺ taken = 31.4 mg			
Metal	Amount added mg	Cu ²⁺ found mg	Error mg
Zn ²⁺	16.3	31.5	+0.1
Ni ²⁺	15.2	31.3	-0.1
Co ²⁺	14.5	31.2	-0.2
Mg ²⁺	12.6	31.5	+0.1
Fe ³⁺	16.1	31.8	+0.4

Cu^{2+} in presence of Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} . The presence of Fe^{3+} interferes during the precipitation of Cu^{2+} . However, the estimation was carried out by sequestering the Fe^{3+} by potassium citrate.

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